
Sorghum Waste as an Adsorbent for the Removal of Nickel, Copper and Chromium ions from Aqueous Solution

Nsikak B. Essien¹, Stevens Odoemelam², Uduak Bassey Essien³

¹Department of Science Technology, Akwa Ibom State Polytechnic, Ikot Osurua, Ikot Ekpene, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria

²Department of Chemistry, Michael Okpara University of Agriculture, Umudike, Abia State, Nigeria

³Department of Chemistry, University of Calabar, Calabar, Cross River State, Nigeria

Abstract This study was carried out to investigate the adsorption efficiency of Sorghum waste for the removal of Ni²⁺, Cu²⁺ and Cr²⁺ from aqueous solution using batch process. The experiment utilized sorghum waste as adsorbent, as an approach to address some levels of resource recovery. The results obtained indicated that sorghum is an effective adsorbent for the removal of Ni²⁺, Cu²⁺ and Cr²⁺ from aqueous solution because it has some useful functional groups (including C=N stretch, N-H O-H and C-H stretches), in addition to other adsorptive properties. The adsorption of these metal ions from aqueous solution is consistent with the mechanism of physical adsorption; it is time, concentration, adsorbent dose and pH dependent. Its adsorption characteristics best fitted the Freundlich, Temkin and Dubinin-Radushkevich adsorption models. From the Freundlich and Temkin models, the extent of interaction was established through the values of their respective adsorption constant. Also the adsorption kinetic of the adsorbates agrees excellently with the pseudo second order kinetic models.

Keywords Heavy metal pollution, water, Ni²⁺, Cu²⁺ and Cr²⁺, adsorption, Sorghum waste

Introduction

The pollution of surface and groundwater with heavy metals has become a serious global concern, both environmentally, as well as with respect to human health [1]. Overabundance of these elements poses severe health risks for humans, and also for other life forms through bioaccumulation along food chains. Therefore, steps should be taken to reduce the amount of such elements in water to acceptable levels. To search for cheaper, eco-friendly adsorbents, Adsorption of Nickel, Copper and chromium ions from aqueous solution, sorghum waste was studied using the batch adsorption process for potential applications in heavy metal ion removal from water. We provide an overview of the current capabilities and important properties of sorghum used for this purpose.

Literature reveals that about 1.2 billion people lack access to safe drinking water while 2.6 billion have little or no sanitation and millions of people die annually, including about 3,900 children resulting from water burned diseases [2].

Several natural and anthropogenic activities like volcanic eruption, landslide, mud slide etc and the one which arises from production, consumption and disposal of products leading to both organic and inorganic pollution respectively are responsible for contamination of most water bodies (including surface and underground water system). Water contamination majorly arises from introduction of pollutant (at concentration that is injurious to the environment)

into the water bodies [3]. Some of these pollutants are insoluble (mostly undissolved particles) and can easily be removed by filtration process. However, most of them (For example heavy metal ions, some microorganism, some chemical pollutants) are soluble and cannot be removed through filtration or other simple processes. Therefore, there is need to source for a low cost, effective, eco-friendly and robust methods of disinfecting and decontaminating water for its useful applications. Adsorption is an established and one of the best options available for the removal of pollutants from water [4].

However, most recent researchers have tried to use modern synthesized, more sensitive and cumbersome adsorbents to remediate heavy metals from an aqueous body. It has been justified that metal organic frameworks (MOFs) can be synthesized and used to effectively remove toxic heavy metals from an aqueous system, however, on the long run, these adsorbents would be costly, cumbersome, problems of specification and lack of easily available reagents may pose a problem in this choice of adsorbent. Shaobinwang *et al* [5] has also shown in his work that Zeolites can also be effectively used as an adsorbent for the remediation of heavy metals in an aqueous environment. Zeolites are mostly found in sedimentary rocks and this points out to the issue of availability, cost implication and abundance over the choice of Zeolites as adsorbents. Nsikak Bassey Essien *et al* [6] previously has shown that Maize cob can also be effectively used as an adsorbent to remove heavy metals using batch adsorption process, however this adsorbent leads to land occupation thereby leaching and depleting away of vital minerals in the soil, this poses a problem back to the environment.

Sorghum is one of the major raw materials used in most breweries. Most often, the waste are thrown away but are readily available, cheap and abundant, therefore in this study, attempt is made to re-use sorghum waste as an adsorbent for heavy metals like Nickel, Copper and Chromium.

Materials and Methods

The sorghum sample was collected from Champion Breweries Limited, in Uyo, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. The substance was sun-dried in an oven at 60°C for 24 hours. The dried substance was then grounded thoroughly in a mortar and sieved into 180µm particle size. All reagents used for the study were of analar grade. The sample was sundried to a constant weight. The dried sample was crushed to powdery form using laboratory mortar and pestle. 400 g of the sample was treated with phosphoric acid, heated to a temperature of 120 °C. The activated sample was repeatedly washed with ionised water until the pH of the filtrate falls between 6.0-6.5. Nickel sulphate, Copper tetraoxosulphate and chromium heptadioxochromate standards were prepared and serially diluted solutions of the respective salts (20, 40, 60, 80 and 100 ppm) were obtained through dilution.

Adsorption Experiment

Equilibrium adsorption of Cu (II), Pd (II) and Zn (II) ions on the maize waste biomass was carried out using 100ml of various concentrations of the adsorbent, different contact time, different metal ion sizes and different concentration of the adsorbate through a batch experimental process. In each case, the concentration of the metal ion adsorbed were determined using AAS (model no AA-6800-SHIMADZU) and the equilibrium amount of metal adsorbed was calculated using the following equation.

$$q_e = \frac{MV(C_0 - C_e)}{1000} \quad 1$$

where q_e is the amount of adsorbate ion adsorbed in milligram per gram of the adsorbent, C_0 is the initial concentration of the metal ion before adsorption process, C_e is the equilibrium concentration of the metal ion in the filtrate after adsorption process and M is the mass in gram of the adsorbent, V is the volume of the solution in ml.

FTIR analysis

FTIR analysis of the sample before and after adsorption of the respective heavy metal ion was carried out using Scimadzu FTIR-8400S Fourier transform infra-red spectrophotometer. The sample were smeared on the sample holder and placed in the sample compartment of the machine. Each sample was prepared in KBr and the analysis

was carried out by scanning the sample through a wave number range of 400 to 4000 cm^{-1} , the resulting spectrum was printed directly from the attached computer and printer.

Results and Discussions

Effect of period of contact and adsorption kinetics

The variation of concentration of Nickel (II), Copper (II) and Chromium (II) ions adsorbed by Sorghum waste with time is shown in Fig. 1. The Figure reveals that the amount of Chromium and Nickel ions adsorbed first increases with time (between the first 20 to 40 minutes) before decreasing (between 40 and 60 minutes), Nickel however shows a marked decrease from 80-100 but Chromium finally increases with increase in the period of contact. On the other hand, the amount of Copper ions adsorbed increases with the period of contact time progressively and was more than the amount of Nickel and Chromium adsorbed by Sorghum Waste. The observed trend may be due to progressive occupation of the available adsorption sites on the surface of the Sorghum waste with increasing concentration of the metal ion. Since the plots for the respective metal ion are not parallel, it follows that the adsorption mechanism depends on the metal ion. Copper ion was the most adsorbed ion, followed by Nickel and lastly by Chromium. Since all the metal ions are divalent. However, it is significant to state that before adsorption, adsorption sites are free but when adsorption starts, the sites are gradually occupied as the period of contact increases and desorption may set in due to competitive process. This explains why the amount of Cr (II) ions adsorbed by Sorghum waste decreases irregularly with time [6].

Figure 1: Variation of the amount of heavy metal ion adsorbed per unit mass of the adsorbent (Sorghum waste) with time

In order to predict the rate of removal of various concentrations of Nickel, Copper and Chromium ions from aqueous solution, adsorption kinetics was used to analyze using solid capacity (a pseudo first-order equation of Lagergren) and solid phase adsorption (a pseudo second-order equation) models. The adsorption of heavy metals onto a non-living cell is generally considered to be a rapid process and according to Eddy and Ekop [7], the Lagergren equation for a pseudo first order kinetics can be written as

$$\log(q_e - q_t) = \log(q_e) - \left(\frac{k_1}{2.303}\right) t_{eq} \quad 1$$

Where q_e and q_t are the amount of metal ion adsorbed (mg g^{-1}) at equilibrium and at any time, t (minutes) respectively. k_1 (min^{-1}) is the equilibrium rate constant of pseudo first-order sorption. The implication of equation 1 is that plotting of $\log(q_e - q_t)$ versus t should be linear with slope and intercept equal to $k_1/2.303$ and $\log(q_e)$ respectively. The Lagergren pseudo first order plots for the adsorption of nickel, copper and chromium ions by sorghum waste is shown in Fig. 2. Values of k_1 , q_e , and R^2 , deduced from the plots are presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Pseudo first and second order rate constants for the adsorption of Nickel (II), Copper and Chromium (VI) ions by Sorghum waste

Cation	q_e (mg/g)	k_1 (min^{-1})	R^2	q_e (mg/g)	K_2 ($\text{gmg}^{-1}\text{min}^{-1}$)	R^2
Cr(II)	0.7302	552.72×10^{-5}	0.4876	14.74926	253.13	0.9733
Ni(II)	1.2965	46.06×10^{-5}	0.0306	24.87562	-20.17	0.9582
Cu(II)	1.6303	2.30×10^{-5}	0.0327	56.81818	-5.49	0.9999

The values of the rate constant, k_1 , equilibrium adsorption capacity, q_e , and the correlation coefficient, R^2 , deduced from Figures 2 and 3 are presented in Table 1. The correlation coefficient for a Pseudo first order kinetic model were found to be very low hence the adsorption of Cr(VI), Cu(II) and Ni(II) ions onto sorghum waste does not obey Lagergreen Pseudo first order kinetic. However, the adsorption of Cr(VI), Cu(II) and Ni(II) ions was consistent with the model.

Figure 2: Variation of $\log(q_e - q_i)$ with t for the adsorption of some heavy metal ions by sorghum waste

On the other hand, a differential form of Pseudo second order kinetic model can be written as shown in equation 2,

$$\frac{t}{q_e} = \left(\frac{1}{k_2 q_e^2} \right) + \left(\frac{1}{q_e} \right) t \quad \text{eq2}$$

The implication of equation 2 is that a plot of $\frac{t}{q_e}$ versus t should be a straight line with slope and intercept equal to $\frac{1}{q_e}$ and $\frac{1}{k_2 q_e^2}$ respectively.

From the results obtained in Table 1, it can be seen that R^2 values for a Pseudo second order model are closer to unity indicating that the adsorption of Cr(VI), Cu(II) and Ni(II) ions onto sorghum wastes is consistent with a Pseudo second order kinetic.

Effect of Adsorbent Dose

The adsorption capacity of different materials especially plants may vary with the different concentration of the adsorbent. Therefore, the effect of different concentrations of the adsorbent on the removal of Nickel, Copper and Chromium ions from aqueous solution was investigated by varying the concentration of the Sorghum waste (between 0.2 to 1.0 g) in the adsorption experiments while pH, time and adsorbate's concentration were held constant. Fig. 4 shows plots for the variation of the amount of nickel, copper and chromium ions adsorbed by various masses of the adsorbent. The plots evidently reveal that copper ions removal first increases as the adsorbent mass increases but after some time, the concentration of heavy metal removed stabilize. However, nickel ion clearly shows that its removal does not depend on increase in adsorption sites or adsorbent dose, chromium ion also shows less dependency as its adsorption increases as the adsorbent dose increase but later stabilize too. This increase in the efficiency of removal with increasing adsorbent dosage may be attributed to the increase in the number of adsorption sites available for adsorption [8]. The observed trend suggest that for a given adsorbent and for a given metal ion, there may be a maximum mass of adsorbent that is needed for effective removal of heavy metal and that beyond the limit, the adsorption may increase or decreases appreciably.

Effect of Concentration of Metal Ions in Solution

Figure 4: Variation of the concentration of adsorbed heavy metal ions with mass of the adsorbent for the adsorption of some heavy metal ions by sorghum waste

Figure 5: Variation of amount of heavy metal ion adsorbed (by sorghum waste) with concentration of the metal ion in solution

Fig. 4 shows plots for the variation of amount of Ni (II), Cu (II) and Cr (VI) ions adsorbed with concentration. The Figure reveals that the amount of nickel, copper and chromium ions adsorbed per unit mass of the adsorbent increases with increasing concentration. Prior to adsorption, transport process such as diffusion may be a driving force, in bringing the ions close to the adsorbent's surface. Increase in concentration can increase the rate of diffusion of the heavy metals to the adsorbent until adsorption equilibrium is established. This explains why the adsorption of nickel, copper and chromium ions increases with increase in the concentration of the heavy metals in the solution. In addition, increase in the rate of diffusion can lead to increase in the sticking probability of the heavy metal ions.

Adsorption Isotherm Analysis

In order to optimized the adsorption characteristics of the heavy metals on sorghum waste biomass, data obtained for the amount of heavy metal ions adsorbed per unit mass of the adsorbent at various concentrations were fitted to different adsorption models including Temkin, Freundlich and DR Isotherm. The tests revealed that Temkin and Freundlich adsorption isotherms best fitted the adsorption characteristics of sorghum waste for chromium, nickel and copper ions. The model establishing the equation for the Freundlich adsorption model can be written in the form given by equation 3,

$$q_e = kC_e^{\frac{1}{n}} \quad 3$$

Where k and n are the Freundlich's constants related to the adsorption capacity and adsorption intensity of the adsorbent used in the system. From the logarithm of both sides of equation 5 equation 6 was obtained upon simplification,

$$\log(q_e) = \log k + \frac{1}{n} \log C_e \quad 4.$$

K and n can be determined from the linear plot of $\log q_e$ (Figure 6) versus $\log C_e$. $1/n$ is indicating the adsorption intensity of heavy metal ion onto the sorbent or surface heterogeneity, becoming more heterogeneous as its value gets closer to zero. A value for $1/n$ below 1 indicates a normal Langmuir isotherm while $1/n$ above 1 is indicative of cooperative adsorption. The Freundlich adsorption constants evaluated from the isotherms for Cr(VI), Ni(II), and Cu(II) ions are presented in Table 2.

Figure 6: Variation of $\log(q_e)$ with $\log(C_e)$ for the adsorption of some heavy metals by sorghum waste
Values of coefficients of correlation R^2 revealed that the Freundlich model fitted the experimental data better since the R values are tending to unity (1). It is significant to note that Freundlich isotherms for the all the metals ions

studied have excellent correlation coefficient and that the isotherms are parallel to each other indicating that the adsorption of Cr(VI), Ni(II) and Cu(II) ions by sorghum waste follows similar mechanism. Calculated values for n were relatively higher than unity for all the heavy metal ions under studied. This suggests the existence of cooperative adsorption [8].

Table 2: Freundlich and Temkin parameters for the adsorption of some heavy metals by sorghum waste biomass

Metal ion	Freundlich parameters			Temkin parameters		
	n	$\log k$	R^2	B	A	R^2
Cr(II)	0.9943	-0.6134	1.0000	27.909	32.95	0.9478
Ni(II)	0.9996	-0.6037	1.0000	27.86	32.86	0.9459
Cu(II)	0.9811	-0.6436	0.9985	28.12	33.47	0.9397

Figure 7: Variation of q_e with $\ln(C_e)$ for the adsorption of some heavy metal ions by sorghum

The adsorption of Cr(VI), Ni(II) and Cu(II) ions by sorghum waste was also found to obey the Temkin adsorption isotherm, which can be written according to equation below

$$q_e = A + B \ln C_e \quad 5$$

Where A is the Temkin adsorption potential, and B is the Temkin constant related to the heat of sorption while q_e (mg/g) and C_e (mg/l) are equilibrium adsorbate concentrations in the solid and aqueous phases respectively. Equation 5 implies that a plots of q_e versus $\ln C_e$ should be linear with slope and intercept equal to B and A respectively. Fig. 7 shows the Temkin isotherms for the adsorption of nickel, copper and chromium ions unto the surface of sorghum waste. Also, the closeness of R_2 values to unity confirms the application and fitting of the Temkin model to the adsorption of the studied heavy metals. Adsorption parameters deduced from the plots are also presented in Table 2. The results obtained indicated that values of Temkin constants were relatively high, suggesting the existent of strong interactions between the adsorbates and the adsorbent. These interactions may be consistent with ion-exchange mechanism or chemical interface between the metal ions and sorghum waste surfaces [9].

Dubinin-Radushkevich (D-R) adsorption model is unique in predicting the mechanism of adsorption of metal ion unto adsorbent, the characteristic porosity of the adsorbent and the apparent energy of adsorption. The Dubinin-Radushkevich (D-R) adsorption model can be expressed according to equation 7

$$\ln q_e = \ln X_m - \beta \left(RT \ln \left(1 + \frac{1}{C_e} \right) \right)^2 \quad 6$$

Where q_e (mg/g) is the concentration of the adsorbate adsorbed in the adsorbent, X_m (mg/g) is the maximum sorption capacity, β (mg^2/kJ^2) is a constant related to the mean adsorption energy, R (kJ/mol/K) is the gas constant and T (K) is the temperature. The bracketed terms in equation 6 represents the polanyl potential while the constant, β is related to the mean adsorption energy (E), which can be expressed as,

$$E = \frac{1}{(2\beta)^2} \quad 7$$

Application of equation 7 to the adsorption of copper, nickel and chromium ions unto sorghum waste surface reveals that plotting of $\ln q_e$ versus $\left(RT \ln \left(1 + \frac{1}{c_e}\right)\right)^2$ were linear with slope and intercept equal to β and $\ln X_m$ respectively. This is shown in Fig. 8. Calculated Dubinin-Radushkevich adsorption parameters are presented in Table 3. The results confirmed that the energies of adsorption of nickel, copper and chromium ions are less than the threshold value of 8 kJ/mol. Therefore, the adsorption of these ions onto sorghum waste is consistent with the mechanism of physical adsorption.

Table 3: D-R parameters for the adsorption of some heavy metals by sorghum waste

Metal ion	$\beta(\text{mg}^2/\text{kJ}^2)$	$\ln(X_m)$	E (kJ/mol)	R^2
Cr(II)	0.66	1640.9	1.23	0.9437
Ni(II)	0.66	1634.5	1.23	0.9389
Cu(II)	0.71	1764.4	1.19	0.9587

Figure 9: Variation of $\log(q_e)$ with ε for the adsorption of some heavy metal ion by sorghum

FTIR Study

FTIR provides a means of detecting functional groups and their fundamental frequencies of vibrations. Application of FTIR in adsorption study can aid in the identification of functional groups that are involved in adsorption or even the mechanism of adsorption. Peaks and frequencies of IR absorption obtained for sorghum waste are presented in Table 4. The spectrum revealed the presence of C–O stretch due to carbonyl group at 1268 cm^{-1} , C=O stretch due to carboxylic at 1655 cm^{-1} , C–Cl stretches due to alkyl group at 692 and OH stretches due to hydroxyl groups at 3528 cm^{-1} respectively. When sorghum waste was used as an adsorbent for Cr ions, the resultant spectrum gave some adsorption frequencies and peaks, which are recorded in Table 5. It reveals that the C=O stretch due to carboxylic group was shifted from 1655 to 1649 cm^{-1} , the C–H stretch due to alkyl group was shifted from 2925 to 2928 cm^{-1} , the O–H stretch due to alcohol was shifted from 3528 to 3420 cm^{-1} . These shifts in frequencies of IR adsorption imply that there is interaction between Cr and the sorghum waste surfaces. On the other hand, the C–O stretch due to

Carbonyl bond, the N-H stretch due to Amine single bond, and the C-N stretch due to amine were missing in the spectrum suggesting that these functional groups were used in the adsorption of Cr (II) ions, Okwunodulu *et al* [10].

Table 4: Peaks and frequencies of IR absorption by sorghum waste

Peak (cm ⁻¹)	Intensity	Assignment
692	68.26	C-Cl stretch due to alkyl halide
1052	49.48	C-O stretch due to alcohol or carboxylic acid
1158	50.10	C-N stretch due to amine
1268	49.13	C-O stretch due to carboxylic acid
1655	33.49	C=O stretch due to carboxylic acid
2925	24.04	C-H stretch due to alkane
3306	22.30	N-H stretch due to amine
3451	22.17	OH stretch due to alcohol
3528	23.46	OH stretch due to alcohol

Table 5: Peaks and frequencies of IR absorption by sorghum waste due to adsorption of Cr(VI) ions

Peak (cm ⁻¹)	intensity	Assignment
629	10.92	C-Cl stretch due to alkyl halide
1646	7.59	C=O stretch due to carboxylic acid
2928	4.93	C-H stretch due to alkane
3420	3.94	OH stretch due to alcohol

Table 6: Peaks and frequencies of IR absorption by sorghum waste due to adsorption of Ni (II) ions

Peak (cm ⁻¹)	intensity	Assignment
679	11.82	C-Cl stretch due to alkyl halide
1050	10.27	C-O stretch due to alcohol or carboxylic acid
1643	8.62	C=O stretch due to carboxylic acid
2929	6.47	C-H stretch due to alkane
3414	5.99	OH stretch due to alcohol

Again when sorghum waste was used as an adsorbent for Ni ions, the resultant spectrum gave some adsorption frequencies and peaks, which are recorded in Table 6. It reveals that the C=O stretch due to carboxylic group was shifted from 1655 to 1643 cm⁻¹, the C-H stretch due to alky group was shifted from 2925 to 2929 cm⁻¹, the O-H stretch due to alcohol was shifted from 3528 to 3414 cm⁻¹, the C-Cl stretch due to alkyl halide was shifted from 692 to 679 cm⁻¹. Again these shifts in frequencies of IR adsorption imply that there was an interaction between Ni and the sorghum waste surfaces. On the other hand, the C-N stretch due to Amine, the N-H stretch due to Amine single bond was missing in the spectrum suggesting that these functional groups were used in the adsorption of Ni (II) ions [10].

The FTIR spectrum of sorghum waste when Cu (II) ions were adsorbed is shown in Table 7, which presents peaks and intensities of IR adsorption by the sorghum waste, in the presence of Cu (II) ions as adsorbates. From the results obtained, it was found that the C-Cl stretch from 692-630cm⁻¹, the C=O stretch due to carboxylic acid was shifted from 1655 to 1646 cm⁻¹, the C-H stretch due to alkane was shifted from 2925 to 2931 cm⁻¹ while the OH stretch due to alcohol was shifted from 3451 to 3420 cm⁻¹. The shifts in frequencies of IR adsorption confirmed that there is interaction between the sorghum waste 'surface and the Cu(II)ions.

Also from the result, it will be noticed that the N-H stretch due to Amine single bond, and the C-N stretch due to amine were missing in the spectrum suggesting that these functional groups were used in the adsorption of Cu (II) ions.

Table 7: Peaks and frequencies of IR absorption by sorghum waste due to adsorption of Cu (II) ions

Peak (cm ⁻¹)	intensity	Assignment
630	12.88	C-Cl stretch due to alkyl halide
1646	7.03	C=O stretch due to carboxylic acid
2931	4.33	C-H stretch due to alkane
3420	3.15	OH stretch due to alcohol

Conclusion

The present study was aimed at investigating the adsorption properties of a cheap, readily available and efficient plant waste like sorghum for Nickel, Chromium and Copper ions. The results of the study revealed that sorghum waste is good adsorbents for heavy metals. These adsorbents functions through the mechanism of physical adsorption and their adsorption properties is consistent with a pseudo second order kinetics while its characteristics is best described by Freundlich, Temkin and Dubinin-Radushkevich adsorption isotherms.

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